

The Cox model and beyond in the prediction of business failure

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Key-words: survival, competing risk, multistage models, machine learning

JEL-codes: C45, C53, G33

Introduction

Cox's semi-parametric proportional hazards regression model has been applied to the prediction of enterprises' failure since 1992 (Narain, 1992) and its well-known extensions to competing risk and multistage models provide useful applications when there are two or more mutually exclusive absorbing states (closure, winding-up, bankruptcy).

Nowadays, machine-learning techniques are becoming more popular and several studies assert their supremacy from the predictive point of view.

The purpose of the present research is the application of new methodologies related to the Cox model and their comparison with the classic survival and competing risk models in the field of corporate default risk prediction.

Methods

Katzman et al. (2018) used a combination of deep learning and the Cox model, developing the DeepSurv module based on the Theano library. Subsequently, Moncado and Torres (2020) improved it with DeepSurvK, while Sonabend et al. (2021) released *mlr3proba*, an R Package for Machine Learning in Survival. Data used to analyze firms' failure in previous research (Caroni and Pierrri, 2020; Pierrri and Caroni, 2020) are employed here to test these new applications of the Cox Model connected to machine learning techniques and results will be compared.

Results

The Cox Model has long been applied in medical fields for prognosis prediction purposes and great advances in deep learning combined with survival analysis have been provided to obtain more and more accurate results.

The test with economic data and the results' comparison with models already developed in this field, will allow determining if and in which cases machine learning techniques can provide more precise estimates and/or more easily interpretable results for economic agents.

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DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10053756